

Food Allergy Awareness Among Kitchen and Service Staff in Food Businesses: A Study in Kütahya and Afyonkarahisar Provinces

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Abstract

Nutrition is one of the most fundamental rights of individuals. However, some foods can cause various symptoms in individuals' digestive and immune systems. Another factor that causes symptoms is the difficulty in digesting or absorbing certain food components. Consumption of such foods can sometimes cause mild symptoms, but it can also lead to serious or even fatal consequences. Individuals with foodborne illnesses should report their condition to businesses and receive information from service and kitchen personnel. Business personnel should be trained on this issue in order to inform customers. Kitchen personnel in businesses should prepare meals meticulously, and business owners should include information on these issues in their menus. Businesses should provide customers with an information text or service personnel that includes information about allergens in their products. The main question of this research is "What are the perceptions of food and beverage business employees towards individuals with food allergies?" is the question. This study aims to examine the level of care that businesses show towards consumers with food allergies in their kitchen practices. The analysis of the data was interpreted by evaluating the arithmetic averages of the participants' responses to each question on a 5-point Likert scale. In the study, 128 food business employees were surveyed using a 5-point Likert scale consisting of questions determined by the researchers as a result of the literature review. Participants were asked 12 general and 5 specific questions. As a result of the study, the question with the highest value with an average of 4.2188 was "Do you think that you can do your best to avoid causing harm to consumers who encounter an allergic situation in kitchen applications?" This finding proves that business employees are ready to do their best not to victimize individuals with food allergies in problems encountered in businesses related to food allergies.

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1. Introduction

Nutrition is defined as the intake of nutrients into the body and their use in necessary processes so that individuals can sustain their lives (Öztürk and Besler, 2012). In some individuals, the foods they consume during the nutrition phase cause various effects on the body and cause discomforts called food allergy or food intolerance, which negatively impact quality of life (Öztürk and Besler, 2012; Köseoğlu, 2020). Food allergy is the immune system's adverse reactions to proteins in foods, causing symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, cramps, pain, gas and diarrhea, swelling of internal organs, and other reactions in the skin, respiratory system, digestive system, and circulatory system (Sampson, 2001; Uz and Türkay, 2006; Karakılıç et al., 2014). Some common allergenic foods include gluten containing cereals, shellfish and products, eggs and egg products, fish and fish products, peanuts and peanut products, soybeans and soybean products, milk and dairy products, nuts, celery and celery products, mustard and mustard products, sesame seeds and sesame seed products, sulfur dioxide and sulfites, lupins and lupin products, molluscs and molluscs products (Akay, 2021).

Food intolerance is the reactions that occur in the body of individuals during the digestion or absorption of the components found in foods, and the most common of these disorders are lactose intolerance, celiac, phenylketonuria, galactosemia, fructose intolerance, and favism (Akoğlu and Oruç, 2018).

Individuals modify their diets in order to avoid the effects that may result from consuming allergenic foods (Kadioğlu, 2017). Since these individuals avoid foods that may cause them discomfort when dining out, they ask staff about the ingredients of menu items. Research conducted in Turkey and worldwide has shown that the knowledge of the kitchen and service staff in businesses regarding food allergies or food intolerances - specifically, whether these products are presented in the menu items is generally at a minimum or moderate level (Mandabach et al., 2005; Ahuja

and Sichere, 2007; Common et al., 2013; Söğüt, et al., 2014; Lokman, 2020). Individuals with food intolerance feel that they are a burden to other individuals in any tourism activity and that individuals without food intolerance cannot empathize with them, while they state that they have a distrust of product labels and restaurants (Schiefert and Matteucci, 2018). In his study, Eren (2020) touched upon issues such as individuals with food allergies and intolerances being isolated and ostracized because they cannot eat in common areas, individuals being made fun of for their illnesses, feeling ashamed when they reject products offered to them due to their sensitivities, food and beverage personnel need to be careful about cross-contamination, the issue of allergies should be taken seriously, there should be a different cuisine where allergenic products are not used, restaurant menus should be improved and dishes that do not include allergenic products should be included in the menus. The problems experienced by individuals with food allergies and intolerances in literature studies were examined and this study was created to measure the perceptions of individuals working in food and beverage businesses on this issue. Since there was no study conducted on food allergies in the cities of Kütahya and Afyonkarahisar, sample groups were selected from these two cities and the aim was to fill the gap in the literature. The purpose of this research is to measure how much food and beverage company personnel know about food allergy or food intolerance, the attitudes of the company personnel towards individuals with this disorder, and the level of knowledge of the personnel about the menu items when individuals with this disorder visit the company. The research also aims to help food and beverage businesses recognize their strengths and weaknesses regarding food allergies and implement improvements accordingly. Another aim of the research is to contribute to individuals with allergies or food intolerance feeling safer and consuming food in companies. The research questions were created by the authors, taking into account the situations that were seen as problems in

previous studies and the findings that emerged. Additionally, the research was conducted with the idea that it would be useful for sector and academic researchers who want to conduct studies in areas such as food safety, food allergy, and foodborne illnesses in the food and beverage sector.

1.1. Conceptual framework

1.1.1. Food allergy

Food allergy is defined as immunological side effects or symptoms of the immune system against proteins in foods (Onyimba et al., 2021). It has been determined that 70% of existing food allergens are in plant-based foods and 30% are in animal-based foods (Tekiner et al., 2020). Frequent allergic reactions to foods can be seen in the form of narrowing of capillaries (redness), increased permeability of vessels (swelling and bloating), contraction of respiratory tract and intestinal muscles (difficulty in breathing and pain), and itching of nerves in the skin (Öztürk and Besler, 2012). Upper and lower respiratory tract symptoms include sneezing, nasal congestion, runny nose, itchy and teary eyes, itchy throat, persistent cough, laryngospasm, and bronchospasm (Karakılıç et al., 2014). The foods that cause these symptoms are known to be dairy products, chocolate, peanuts, almonds, hazelnuts, shrimp, and alcoholic beverages (Özdağlı, 2009). Common gastrointestinal symptoms include nausea, vomiting, cramp-like abdominal pain, diarrhea, and abdominal bloating (Karakılıç et al., 2014). In food-borne allergies, the maximum negative and high response of the immune system to the food is known as shock reactions. Anaphylaxis is defined as a hypersensitivity state that causes symptoms such as simultaneous involvement of multiple organs, vomiting, abdominal pain, and respiratory failure, and these symptoms show their effects within two hours after consuming the allergenic food (Tercanlı and Atasever, 2021). Food allergies are usually caused by the immunoglobulin E (IgE) antibody, which is a member of the immune system. When individuals with food allergies ingest the allergenic food, the immune system begins to

produce IgE antibodies. While the body's first encounter with this allergen does not cause an allergic reaction, previously produced IgE antibodies can be made to recognize the allergen on subsequent encounters. The main causes of pharmacological food allergies are reactions caused by food products that contain or release histamine, food products that release tyramine, dopamine, norepinephrine, phenylethylamine and serotonin (Ortolani and Pastorello, 2006). Some of the diseases that occur due to these food allergies are known as primary pulmonary hemosiderosis syndromes that occur involuntarily with urticaria, atopic dermatitis, eosinophilic gastrointestinal disorders, protein-losing enteropathy, celiac disease and milk allergy (Ebisawa et al., 2020). The most common allergenic foods stated by the FDA are milk, eggs, fish, shellfish, tree nuts, peanuts, wheat, and soy (Tatlı, 2019). In addition to these products, gluten-containing grains: wheat, rye, barley, oats or their hybrid varieties and their products, celery and celery products, mustard and mustard products, sesame and sesame seed products, sulfur dioxide and sulfites, lupins and lupin products, mollusks and their products can also cause allergic reactions (Akay, 2021). Spices, which are among the products that can be listed in this group, are known to be among the products that can cause food allergies. In addition to these, chocolate, honey, coffee, tea, some beverages containing gas and fruit juice, and alcoholic beverages are also foods that cause food allergies (Öztürk and Besler, 2012). Serum albumin immunoglobulin, myosin light chain kinase, parvalbumin, enolase, and aldose in meat are known to cause food allergy (Tercanlı and Atasever, 2021). Research has found that soy allergy begins in infancy and develops until the age of three. It is observed that this allergy can decrease in individuals with soy allergy until the age of ten (Savage et al., 2010). The protein that causes allergic reactions to foods such as plums, hazelnuts, kiwi, carrots, apples, spinach, and pears is bet v 1, a protein isolated from birch tree pollen that grows widely in Northern European countries (Güzelsoy, 2021).

1.1.2 Food Intolerance

Food intolerance is defined as the reactions of the digestive system of individuals to certain components in the food taken into the body (Akay and Yılmaz, 2020). The difference between intolerance and allergy is that intolerance affects the digestive system, while allergy affects the immune system. Reactions caused by food intolerance are not life-threatening, but food allergy can cause serious symptoms and can be life-threatening (Lokman, 2020).

Food intolerance is caused by multiple factors including, toxic substances, food additives (colorants, sweeteners), psychological effects of traumatic events, genetic predispositions, characteristics of the allergenic product, frequency of consumption, the individual's immune system, demographic factors, anxiety, various surgical procedures and operations, and the absence of certain enzymes in the body (Akay and Yılmaz, 2020; Albayrak and Korkmaz, 2022). The most common intolerance in this group caused by enzymatic deficiencies is lactose intolerance caused by lactase deficiency (Lokman, 2020). Caffeine intolerance is a genetic disorder in which individuals cannot metabolize caffeine found in foods such as coffee and cocoa, and symptoms such as increased heart rate, insomnia, and irritability. Salicylates, found in foods such as tomatoes, eggplants, peppers, fruits, vegetables, spices, and certain medicines cause itching, runny nose, and diarrhea in individuals. Biogenic amines (such as histamine, tyramine, and phenylethylamine), which are present in fermented vegetables, meat, and dairy products, cannot be metabolized due to the absence of necessary enzymes. Sulfites and sulfates used as gelatin in food products; Cause itching, cough, runny nose, low blood pressure and diarrhea in individuals. Food intolerance is also refers to symptoms such as gas, bloating, abdominal pain and diarrhea, which occur when fructose, sorbitol, and oligo-, di-, monosaccharides, and polyols pass directly into the large intestine without being digested (Yıldız, 2021).

1.1.3 Applications that can be done to prevent food allergy and food intolerance cases in food businesses

Any individual who visits a food and beverage business should inform the staff about their food allergies. However, if the customer experiences allergic symptoms after consuming food despite informing the staff, the establishment is considered responsible. In order to prevent these incidents, the use of Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) and Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP), which are accepted worldwide, are effective. Kitchen staff and service personnel should be informed about allergenic foods. In food producing businesses, thanks to the Food Codex Food Labeling and Consumer Information Regulation, it has become mandatory to inform the consumer about allergenic information for food products. Businesses should indicate on the menu if allergenic ingredients or allergenic side foods are added during food production and preparation processes. The service personnel should know the menu items well and should be able to inform the customer about the foods containing allergens. Kitchen staff should carefully read the order form and pay close attention to the packaging used in meal preparation, cross-contamination, food hygiene, preventing the accidental introduction of allergenic ingredients, and the cleaning of preparation and cooking equipment. If allergenic food has entered the meal, the meal should be remade. Business owners should list the allergenic ingredients under each meals on the menus. Even the vapors produced while cooking allergenic foods can cause serious reactions in some allergic individuals due to inhalation (Parlak, 2018).

Heat treatment of foods can sometimes reduce or increase the effects of allergenic substances because it causes changes in the protein structures of foods. It has been observed that the allergenic potential of peanuts increases in high-temperature heat treatment applications or roasting applications, while boiling and frying reduce this effect (Kocatepe and Turan, 2012; Özcan, Delikanlı and Yıldız, 2015). Heat treatment methods

attract attention in food allergies due to changes in the structure of proteins as a result of heat treatment. The variables that emerge as a result of heat treatment in allergenic foods are affected by the structural properties of the proteins, the duration and degree of heat treatment, and the physicochemical properties of the environment in which the food is located. For example, a roasting process at 140 degrees for 40 minutes reduces the allergenicity of heat-resistant Cor a 1.04 by a hundred times. Moist and dry heat treatment methods reduce the effects of potential allergens Ara h 1 and Ara h 2 (Özcan, Delikanlı and Yıldız, 2015). However, heat treatment applications can sometimes reduce the risk of food allergy and sometimes increase it. It has been observed that some fish do not pose an allergen risk when consumed fresh, but create an allergen risk after heat treatment (Davis, Smales and James, 2001).

In a study conducted abroad to measure the education and knowledge levels of individuals working in restaurants about food allergies, cross-contamination was given as the primary factor among the reasons why food allergies occur in restaurants. It is recommended that all employees in the restaurant should be continuously sent to food allergy training and that individuals who complete the training should be given incentive awards (Lee and Sozen, 2016).

In the legislation published by the European Union, labeling of food allergen information has been made mandatory and in addition, it imposes a special obligation on food businesses to prevent food-borne hazards. It is stated that allergen risk management should be carried out in the production and retail stages of food and its compliance with quality criteria should be inspected. The study emphasizes that all employees in all stages from field to plate should receive training (Muraro et al., 2014). It is emphasized that attention should be paid to the formation of allergic reactions caused by the packaging in which the food is stored during the takeaway service stage and that attention should be paid to menu labeling (Zhang et al., 2022).

3. Material and Methods

This research is a study aimed at examining the sensitivity shown to consumers with food allergies in the kitchen practices of businesses. The research was carried out with the approval of the Kütahya Dumlupınar University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research Publication Ethics Committee. At the beginning of the study, the questions and parametric values, determined in accordance with ethical principles by researchers, who reviewed the literature written on food allergy and food intolerance, were taken into consideration. Before starting the survey, participants were informed about the research and it was explained that their personal data would be collected for research purposes only. After the explanation, individuals who wanted to participate in the survey filled out the survey form. The analysis of the data was interpreted by evaluating the arithmetic means of the participants' responses to each question on a 5-point Likert scale. Using the 5-point Likert scale in the research reveals the feature that the items in the scale want to measure and provides a total score for the internal features to be measured (Bayat, 2014). The scale was rated as; 1: I don't know at all 2: I know a little 3: I know 4: I know well 5: I know very well. Accordingly, the findings obtained were analyzed and concluded. In the study, 128 food and beverage business employees working in cafes, restaurants, family businesses, and tradesmen's restaurants were reached using a 5-point Likert scale. Among these employees, the chi-square test was used in the analysis of the relevant factors in determining the degree of sensitivity shown to consumers with food allergies by the employees working in the positions of assistant chef, cook, domi chief, business manager, business partner, business owner, cashier, pastry chef, kitchen warehouse, kitchen staff, patisserie bellboy, patisserie staff, assistant cook, barista, waiter, pastry assistant, personnel manager, hot chef, cold chef, supervisor, chef, head waiter, and shop assistant. They were asked 12 general questions about food allergy and food intolerance and 5 specific questions including demographic information. The sample was

directed to participants living in Kütahya and Afyonkarahisar provinces and working in food and beverage businesses. The Likert survey method was used as the research technique. The reason for the researchers using the technique is to reveal the level of knowledge of the employees about general information about food intolerance and food allergy. The research data was analyzed using the statistical program called SPSS 26. Cronbach's Alpha statistical test was applied to the reliability of the study in the spss program. In addition, statistical tests were applied on the item statistics regarding the Food Allergy Perceptions of Kitchen and Service Workers and the demographic characteristics of the participants. The ability of the measurement tool used to measure the desired feature and its sub-dimensions in accordance with its purpose is called content validity. Content validity is determined by the extent to which the questions created represent the measurement of the desired behaviors, tendencies and perceptions in an integrated manner. In this research, measuring according to the level of the sample group and preparing the survey questions in accordance with the purpose of the study prove that content validity is achieved (Garip, 2023). A clear understanding by the participants of the measurement tool used by the researcher ensures face validity (Sahı, 2018). The fact that the questions of this study were written in a clear, clear and understandable language proves that face validity was achieved. The sample group was selected by convenience sampling method. In the convenience sampling

method, individuals who are economical and easy to reach are selected for the sample group (Yağar and Dökme, 2018). 400 questionnaire forms were distributed to food and beverage establishments in Kütahya and Afyonkarahisar provinces. Of the questionnaires collected, 128 questionnaire forms were filled out completely and appropriately for the study. A similar study, Kılınç (2022), was taken as a reference in determining the appropriateness of the sample group number for this study. Kılınç, (2022) measured the perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors of 118 accommodation business employees towards food allergy and the Cronbach alpha value of the study was found to be “.791”. In the analysis of the questionnaires in this study, Cronbach α “.663” was found. This value proves that the study provides reliability. In studies conducted, Cronbach α coefficient is used to determine scale reliability. The most widely accepted classification of the Cronbach α coefficient is as follows:

If $0.00 < \alpha < 0.40$, the scale is not reliable.

If $0.40 < \alpha < 0.60$, the reliability of the scale is low.

If $0.60 < \alpha < 0.80$, the scale is sufficiently reliable.

If $0.80 < \alpha < 1$, the scale is highly reliable (Özdamar, 2004).

The Cronbach α value of this study is “.663”. The Cronbach α value of the study shows that it is a sufficiently reliable scale (Table 1).

Table 1. Cronbach's alpha scale

Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	N of items
.663	.666	12

4. Findings and Discussion

In this part of the study, the findings and literature studies regarding the perceptions of kitchen and service employees towards food

allergy in food and beverage establishments are compared and discussed. Table 2 below includes findings regarding the gender, education level, and profession of the individuals participating in the survey.

Table 2. Findings regarding demographic characteristics of participants

Gender	Frequency	%	Educational Status	Frequency	%
Females	53	41.4	Primary school	1	0.8
Male	75	58.6	Secondary school	3	2.3
			High school	36	28.1
			Open high school	3	2.3
			University	81	63.3
			Associate's degree	1	0.8
			Masters Degree	1	0.8
			Open Education	2	1.6

Table 3. Statistical data about the department where the participants work

Job	Frequency	%	Job	Frequency	%
Assistant chef	1	0.8	Assistant cook	9	7.0
Cook	23	18.0	Barista	14	10.9
Domi chief	1	0.8	Waiter	41	32.0
Business manager	3	2.3	Pastry assistant	1	0.8
Business partner	1	0.8	Personnel manager	1	0.8
Business owner	9	7.0	Hot chef	1	0.8
Cashier	5	3.9	Cold chef	1	0.8
Pastry chef	1	0.8	Supervisor	1	0.8
Kitchen warehouse	1	0.8	Chef	7	5.5
Kitchen staff	1	0.8	Head waiter	1	0.8
Patisserie bellboy	1	0.8	Shop assistant	3	2.3
Patisserie staff	1	0.8			

Table 4. Item statistics on food allergy perceptions of kitchen and service staff

Questions	Mean	Standard deviation
Do you know about food allergies?	3.4922	1.31614
Do you have information about the metabolization processes of food?	2.7891	1.29598
Is food allergy a disorder that develops in connection with the immune system?	3.1328	1.35374
Do you have information about the expression immunoglobulin E?	1.8359	1.24089
Is food allergy a condition that only occurs in childhood?	2.5703	1.38430
Do you have information about food items that cause allergic reactions?	3.1953	1.35192
Do you provide preliminary information to consumers who show food allergies?	3.3359	1.39333
Do you direct your trained employee to communicate with consumers with food allergies?	3.4766	1.41958
Do you think you can do your best not to victimize consumers who encounter an allergic situation in kitchen applications?	4.2188	1.11495
Do you think that restaurants have menus that can benefit consumers with food allergies?	3.0391	1.41645
Is allergen information presented to consumers through means such as posters, blackboards, menus?	2.7031	1.50254
Do you think you are very sensitive to consumers with food allergies?	3.5781	1.31980

The personal findings obtained from the survey used in the study that 75 males and 53 females participated, with ages ranging from 18 to 57. The individuals participating in the survey have between 1 month and 25 years of experience in businesses. The education levels of the survey participants are as follows: 36 high school graduates, 3 open high school graduates, 81 university graduates, 1 associate degree holder, 2 open education students, 1 master's degree holder, 1 primary school

graduate, and 3 secondary school graduates. The participants hold various positions including of assistant chef, cook, domi chief, business manager, business partner, business owner, cashier, pastry chef, kitchen warehouse, kitchen staff, patisserie bellboy, patisserie staff, assistant cook, barista, waiter, pastry assistant, personnel manager, hot chef, cold chef, supervisor, chef, head waiter and shop assistant.

Table 5. Frequency and percentage statistics of items related to food allergy perceptions of kitchen and service personnel (n:128)

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
	Don't know at all	I know a little	I know	I know well	I know very well
Do you know about food allergies?	13 (%10.2)	18 (%14.1)	27 (%21.1)	33 (%25.8)	37 (%28.9)
Do you have information about the metabolization processes of food?	29 (%22.7)	23 (%18.0)	35 (%27.3)	28 (%21.9)	13 (%10.2)
Is food allergy a disorder that develops in connection with the immune system?	21 (%16.4)	23 (%18.0)	25 (%19.5)	36 (%28.1)	23 (%18)
Do you have information about the expression immunoglobulin E?	75 (%58.6)	25 (%19.5)	11 (%8.6)	8 (%6.3)	9 (7.0)
Is food allergy a condition that only occurs in childhood?	39 (%30.5)	29 (%22.7)	23 (%18.0)	22 (%17.2)	15 (%11.7)
Do you have information about food items that cause allergic reactions?	19 (%14.8)	22 (%17.2)	29 (%22.7)	31 (24.2)	27 (%21.1)
Do you provide preliminary information to consumers who show food allergies?	17 (%13.3)	22 (%17.2)	26 (%20.3)	27 (%21.1)	36 (%28.1)
Do you direct your trained employee to communicate with consumers with food allergies?	18 (%14.1)	15 (%11.7)	26 (%20.3)	26 (%20.3)	43 (%33.6)
Do you think you can do your best not to victimize consumers who encounter an allergic situation in kitchen applications?	4 (%3.1)	9 (%7.0)	17 (%13.3)	23 (%18.0)	75 (%58.6)
Do you think that restaurants have menus that can benefit consumers with food allergies?	27 (%21.1)	18 (%14.1)	32 (%25.0)	25 (%19.5)	26 (%20.3)
Is allergen information presented to consumers through means such as posters, blackboards, menus?	42 (%32.8)	21 (%16.4)	19 (%14.8)	25 (%19.5)	21 (%16.4)
Do you think you are very sensitive to consumers with food allergies?	11 (%8.6)	19 (%14.8)	26 (%20.3)	29 (%22.7)	43 (%33.6)

"Do you know about food allergies?" Among the answers given to the question, the answer with the highest value is "I know" with a rate of %28.9. Ajala et al. (2010) conducted a survey to measure the knowledge of managers and food processors working in

supermarket chain restaurants about food allergies. It was determined that %73 of restaurant employees were knowledgeable about food allergies. Although the findings of Ajala et al. (2010) study on food allergy knowledge are similar to the findings of this

study, the percentage of people who answered "I know" in this study has a lower value. The analysis average rate of the answers given by 128 employees to the question "Do you know about the processes of food metabolism?" based on a 5-point Likert scale is in the 2.7891. The answer with the highest percentage among the answers to the question is "I know" with %27.3. "Is food allergy a disease that develops in connection with the immune system?" Among the answers given to the question, the highest percentage is "I know" with %28.1. In a similar study, Wen and Kwon (2017) aimed to measure the communication and behavior of full service restaurant waiters with individuals with food allergies. Wen and Kwon (2017) stated in their study that "food allergy occurs as a result of the immune system reacting negatively to a food." The answer with the highest rate among the answers given to the question was "correct" with %55.7. Although this finding of Wen and Kwon, (2017) study is similar to the finding of our study, the percentage of those responding "I know" has a lower value in this study. 128 employees asked "Do you know about the expression Immunoglobulin E?" The average of the answers given to the question is 1.8359 on a 5-point Likert scale. Among the answers given to the question, the answer with the highest percentage was " Don't know at all " with %58.6. The analysis average rate of the answers given by 128 employees based on a 5-point Likert scale to the question "Is food allergy a condition that only develops in childhood?" is in the range of 2.5703. Among the answers given to the question, the answer with the highest percentage was " Don't know at all " with %30.5. The analysis average rate of the answers given by 128 employees based on a 5-point Likert scale to the question "Do you have information about food substances that cause allergic reactions?" is in the range of 3.1953. Among the answers given to the question, the answer with the highest percentage was " I know well " with %24.2. The analysis average rate of the answers given by 128 employees to the question "Do you provide preliminary information to consumers who show food allergies?" is in the range of

3.3359. Among the answers given to the question, the answer with the highest percentage was " I know very well " with %28.1. The average rate of the analysis of the responses of 128 employees to the question "Do you direct your trained employees to communicate with consumers with food allergies?" according to the 5-point Likert scale is 3.4766. The response with the highest percentage among the responses given to the question was "I know very well" with %33.6.

The average of the analysis of the responses given by 128 employees to the question "Do you think you do your best not to victimize consumers who encounter an allergic situation in kitchen applications?" according to the 5-point Likert scale was 4.2188, which is the item with the highest value. The response with the highest percentage among the responses given to the question was "I know very well" with %58.6.

In this study, the following question was asked: Do you think restaurants have menus that can benefit consumers with food allergies? The average analysis rate of the participants' responses to the question is between 3.0391 and the "I know" perception level. Albayrak and Korkmaz (2022) found in their study that only 2 of 19 food and beverage businesses included options suitable for food allergies and intolerances in their menus. Therefore, this finding of the study differs from the literature. Therefore, this finding of the research differs from the literature.

The analysis average rate of the answers given by 128 employees to the question "Is allergen information presented to consumers through means such as posters, blackboards, menus?" based on a 5-point Likert scale is 2.7031 and is in the range of "I know a little" perception level. In the study of Albayrak and Korkmaz (2022), the practices of 19 food and beverage establishments in Gökçeada regarding food allergies were examined. The findings that food allergenic products were not shown on the menus of the restaurants and that there were no allergen tables are similar to the results of this article. Borchgrevink et al. (2009) applied a survey technique to 58 food

and beverage establishments in order to measure their knowledge about food allergies and food intolerance policies. The absence of a written document in restaurants to inform individuals with food allergies and food intolerance is similar to the results of our research.

The analysis average rate of the answers given by 128 employees based on a 5-point Likert scale to the question "Do you think you are very sensitive to consumers with food allergies?" is in the "3.5781. Among the answers given to the question, the answer with the highest percentage was " I know very well " with %33.6. The reasons why the employees did not know the answers to some questions while answering the questions were that they did not receive any training on this subject, the employees were studying or not graduating from food fields such as tourism or gastronomy, they had not come across an individual with an allergy before or the individuals did not tell them. The survey revealed ideas and comments such as business owners and managers will be more sensitive about this subject and the business personnel will be informed about this subject not only for individuals with allergies but also because they are curious.

5. Conclusion

The question "Do you have information about the expression of Immunoglobulin E?" was not found in previous literature studies. Accordingly, by adding this question to the survey of the study, it was aimed to raise awareness about the Immunoglobulin E antibody among individuals working in food and beverage businesses. The finding about whether allergen warnings are included in the menus of food and beverage establishments is supported by other literature studies. In line with this finding, it is suggested that the menus of food and beverage establishments should be updated to include foods made with products that include allergen information and do not contain allergenic products. In the analysis of the answers given to the question "Do you have information about food allergies?" the average

answer is "I know." In line with this finding, it is suggested that studies can be conducted on the content of food allergy training to be given to food and beverage business personnel. The limitations of this study are that the sample group consists of 128 people and covers food and beverage businesses in the cities of Kütahya and Afyonkarahisar. It is recommended that researchers who will conduct a study later should conduct a study with a larger sample group and what should be done in food and beverage businesses regarding food allergies. Another suggestion is that studies can be conducted to compare the practices applied abroad for individuals with food allergies and intolerances with the practices in Turkey. Finally, suggestions that can be given to businesses in food and beverage businesses to ensure the satisfaction of customers with allergies:

- ✓ Providing mandatory training to service, kitchen and counter personnel about food allergies, food intolerances and food products that cause allergic reactions.
- ✓ Listing allergenic products in packaged products that enter the kitchen and ensuring that food preparation staff read the labels of these products again when they receive them and then add them to the meal.
- ✓ Adding lists of allergenic foods to menus under dishes containing these products. Creating standard menus that include allergen information.
- ✓ Selecting service staff from individuals who have received training in the field or training employees on this information.
- ✓ A section of the kitchen should have counters and equipment only for individuals with food allergies and vegans, and the food ordered by these individuals should be prepared there.
- ✓ A strong ventilation system should be established, as even the smell of allergic foods can bother individuals with allergies.
- ✓ In businesses that take orders digitally, an application should be created to remove allergenic products from the meal and individuals should be able to remove the allergic product from the meal.

✓ Service staff should ask every customer who comes in whether they have an allergy.

Authors' Contribution Declaration

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Conflict of Interest Declaration

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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